

University of Novi Sad
**INSTITUTE
OF FOOD
TECHNOLOGY
IN NOVI SAD**

feed
congress

16-18 October, 2024
Novi Sad, Serbia

5th

**INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
FOOD TECHNOLOGY,
QUALITY AND SAFETY**

e-ABSTRACT BOOK

ISBN 978-86-7994-063-6

V INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS “FOOD TECHNOLOGY, QUALITY AND SAFETY”, 16-18 OCTOBER 2024, NOVI SAD, REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Publisher

University of Novi Sad
Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad
Bulevar cara Lazara 1
21000 Novi Sad
Republic of Serbia

Main editor

Dr Ljubiša Šarić

Editor

Dr Renata Kovač
Dr Nataša Ćurčić
Dr Bojana Šarić

Abstract Review

All abstracts are peer-reviewed and supervised by the International Scientific Committee

Technical editor

Dragana Tomanić
Milica Vidosavljević

Cover

Boris Bartula, BIS, Novi Sad, Serbia

Organization of Congress:

- INSTITUTE OF FOOD TECHNOLOGY IN NOVI SAD, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Co-Organizers of Congress:

- SHANDONG AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY, People's Republic of China
- INSTITUTE OF MEAT HYGIENE AND TECHNOLOGY, University of Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

Congress is supported by:

- Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Provincial Secretariat for Regional Development, Interregional Cooperation and Local Self-Government, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia
- Food and Feed Research, Journal of the Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Congress President:

Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

General sponsor: Analysis d.o.o. – Novi Beograd, Republic of Serbia

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

President:

Tamara Dapčević Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Members:

Aleksandar Marić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Jovanović Galović, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia

Aleksandra Mišan, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Aleksandra Nikolić, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Aleksandra Novaković, Faculty of Education in Bijeljina, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Alexandrina Sirbu, FMMAE Râmnicu Vâlcea, Constantin Brâncoveanu University of Pitesti, Romania

Alena Stupar, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Anamarija Mandić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Anita Klaus, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Antonio Moretti, Institute of Sciences of Food Production, National Council of Research CNR-ISPA, Italy

Biljana Pajin, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Biljana Stojanovska Dimzoska, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Bojan Butinar, Institute for Olive culture, Science and Research Centre Koper, ZRS Koper, Slovenia

Bojana Kokić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Bojana Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Branislav Šojić, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Breda Jakovac Strajn, Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

Brijesh Tiwari, Teagasc - Agriculture and Food Development Authority, Ireland

Cristina M. Rosell, Department of Food and Human Nutritional Sciences, University of Manitoba, Canada

Dapeng Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China

Dejan Dragan Miladinović, Center for Feed Technology, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway

Diego A. Moreno-Fernández, CEBAS-CSIC, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain

Dragomir Catalin, National Institute for Research and Development in Animal Biology and Nutrition, Romania

Dragan Milić, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dragana Plavšić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dragana Ubiparip Samek, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Dubravka Škrobot, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Elena Velickova Nikova, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Fatih Ozogul, Faculty of Fisheries, Cukurova University, Turkey

Feng Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China

Fatjon Hoxha, Agricultural University of Tirana, Albania
Filip Kulić, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Francesco Marra, Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Salerno, Italy
Francisco Barba, University of Valencia, Spain
Giuseppina Avantaggiato, Institute of Sciences of Food Production, Bari, Italy
Gordana Dragović Lukić, Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Gul Ebru Orhun, Canakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Turkey
Hanxue Hou, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Igor Tomašević, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Ilias Giannenas, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Greece
Ines Banjari, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Ioannis Mourtzinou, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece
Ivan Pavkov, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ivana Čabarkapa, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ivana Živković, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia
Jana Klopčevska, Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Jasmina Lazarević, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Miljanić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Tomić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelka Pleadin, Croatian Veterinary Institute, Croatia
Josip Lepes, Gal Ferenc University, Hungary
Jovana Kos, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Kojić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Vunduk, Institute of General and Physical Chemistry, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Jurislav Babić, Faculty of Food Technology Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Katarina Šavikin, Institute for Medicinal Plants Research "Dr. Josif Pančić, Serbia
Katerina Dodovska Blagoevska, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine – Skopje, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Kaye Burgess, Teagasc - Agriculture and Food Development Authority, Ireland
Krzysztof Klinecicz, Faculty of Management, University of Warsaw, Poland
Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Louise Dye, Institute for Sustainable Food, University of Sheffield, UK
Luciano Pinotti, Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Science (DIVAS), University of Milan, Italy
Maja Matoša Kočar, Agricultural Institute Osijek, University of Osijek, Croatia
Maja Rapajić, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Marcela Šperanda, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences in Osijek, Josip Juraj Strossmayera University of Osijek, Croatia
Marco Garcia-Vaquero, UCD School of Agriculture and Food Science, University College Dublin, Ireland
Marija Milašinović Šeremešić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Marijana Sakač, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Matteo Ottoboni, Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Science (DIVAS), University of Milan, Italy

Mia Eeckhout, Department of Food Technology, Safety and Health, Ghent University, Belgium
Mian N. Riaz, Dept. of Food Science and Technology, Texas A&M University, USA
Mihaela Jurdana, Institute for Kinesiology Research, Science and Research Centre Koper, ZRS Koper, Slovenia
Milan Ilić, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia
Milan Vraneš, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milena Stranska, Faculty of Food and Biochemical Technology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czech Republic
Milica Pojić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milivoj Radojčin, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miloš Pelić, Scientific Veterinary Institute Novi Sad, Serbia
Miona Belović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miroљjub Barać, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Miroslav Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Mladen Brnčić, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Mladenka Pestorić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Ćurčić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Jovanović Lješković, Faculty of Pharmacy Novi Sad, University Business Academy, Serbia
Nebojša Ilić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nemanja Teslić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nikola Tomić, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Nikolina Ćukelj Mustač, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Olivera Đuragić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Omer Said Toker, Chemical and Metallurgical Engineering Faculty, Food Engineering Department, Yildiz Technical University Istanbul, Turkey
Patrik Drid, Faculty of Sport and Physical Education, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pedro Silva, Instituto de Medicina Molecular, University of Lisbon, Portugal
Peter Raspor, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
Predrag Ikonić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Qingguo Wang, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Rada Jevtić Mučibabić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Relja Suručić, Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Renata Kovač, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ružica Tomičić, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Sandra Zavadlav, Department of Food Technology, Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, Croatia
Sanja Belić, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Saša Despotović, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Slađana Rakita, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Slobodan Gadžurić, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Spiros Paramithiotis, Department of Biological Applications and Technologies, University of Ioannina, Greece
Szabo Balazs, Cereal Research Nonprofit Ltd., Hungary
Szabolcs Halazsi, Faculty of Pedagogy, Gal Ferenc University, Hungary

Tatjana Peulić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Verica Dragović-Uzelac, Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, Croatia
Vesna Đorđević, Institute of Meat Hygiene and Technology, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Viktor Nedović, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Wei Chen, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Xiaoyong Sun, College of Information Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Xuguang Qiao, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Yilun Chen, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Yimin Zhang, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Žarko Kevrešan, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zhixiang Xu, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Zlata Kralik, Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
Zorica Stojanović, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zorica Tomičić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zsuzsanna Jakabné Sándor, Research Centre for Aquaculture and Fisheries (HAKI), Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Hungary

EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE

Bojana Kokić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Bojana Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Kos, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ljubiša Šarić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Predrag Ikonić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Tamara Dapčević Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

President:

Pavle Jovanov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Members:

Aleksandar Marić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Aleksandra Bajić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Alena Stupar, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Biljana Cvetković, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Bojana Radić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Branislava Đermanović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Danka Dragojlović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dragana Tomanić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dragana Plavšić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dragana Ubiparip, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Ivana Čabarkapa, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Miljanić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jelena Tomić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Delić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Jovana Kojić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Lidija Perović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milana Matić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Milica Vidosavljević, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miloš Županjac, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miona Belović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Miroslav Hadnađev, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Đerić Ilić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nataša Ćurčić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nedeljka Spasevski, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nemanja Teslić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Nikola Maravić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Olivera Šimurina, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Olja Todorić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Petar Ilić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Radmila Radović, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Renata Kovač, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Strahinja Vidosavljević, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Tatjana Peulić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Viktor Stojkov, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Vojislav Banjac, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Zorica Tomičić, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Fan Liu, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Feng Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Kang Xu, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Qingqing Li, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China
Yannan Chen, College of Food Science and Engineering, Shandong Agricultural University, China

EVALUATION OF TOCOPHEROL VARIABILITY IN WILD HELIANTHUS SPECIES: A GENETIC RESOURCE FOR SUNFLOWER BREEDING

Jelena Jocković*, Nada Grahovac, Siniša Jocić, Milan Jocković, Sandra Cvejć, Dušica Jovičić, Ana Marjanović Jeromela

Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Maksima Gorkog 30, Novi Sad, Serbia

*Corresponding author:

E-mail address: jelena.jockovic@nsseme.ns.rs

Tocopherols are one of the most important bioactive compounds which improve the quality of the oil regards to their antioxidant properties. Considering that wild *Helianthus* species are a very important source of genes for the breeding of cultivated sunflower the aim of this research was to evaluate the variability in tocopherol content and composition within a germplasm collection. The evaluated germplasm included seven annual *Helianthus* species (*H. annuus*, *H. argophyllus*, *H. debilis*, *H. neglectus*, *H. niveus*, *H. petiolaris* and *H. praecox*). Oil samples were extracted using a hydraulic press. Tocopherol quantification was performed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) on a Nucleosil 100-5 NH₂ column with fluorescence detection ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=280$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}}=340$ nm). The mobile phase comprised n-hexane/ethyl acetate (70/30, v/v) at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Tocopherols were identified and confirmed based on their relative retention values and maximum absorption peaks, using 20 μ l injection volumes. The obtained results of the comparative tocopherol analysis revealed significant variability among wild *Helianthus* species. Tocopherol content averaged 333.5 mg kg⁻¹ seed in the all analyzed species, with an average profile of 328.56 mg kg⁻¹ (98.5%) of alpha-tocopherol, which is dominant. Only in species *H. annuus* and *H. niveus*, in small concentrations (6.83 mg kg⁻¹ and 6.65 mg kg⁻¹), beta-tocopherol was identified. By applying of the Principal Components Analysis the species with the lowest tocopherol content (*H. praecox* 133.59 mg kg⁻¹ and *H. niveus* mg 238.23 kg⁻¹) and the species with the highest content (*H. annuus* 458.11 mg kg⁻¹ and *H. neglectus* 459.35 mg kg⁻¹) were clearly distinguished. The obtained results could serve as a tool to select species with high concentration of these bioactive compounds in design management strategies to obtain them in the breeding programs of cultivated sunflower.

Keywords: Wild sunflower, germplasm, oil, tocopherol

Acknowledgements: This work is supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of Republic of Serbia, grant number 451-03-68/2022-14/ 200032, by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, through IDEAS project "Creating climate smart sunflower for future challenges" (SMARTSUN) grant number 7732457, by Centre of Excellence for Innovations in Breeding of Climate-Resilient Crops - Climate Crops, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, Serbia, and the by the European Commission through Horizon Europe programme project CARINA (grant agreement 101081839) and Twinning Western Balkans project CROPINNO (grant number 101059784). Project HelEx, grand number 101081974, funded by EC.